

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178875>

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari chet tillarini o'qitishda muhim ro'l o'ynaydi, bu esa o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Bu maqolada til o'rganish jarayonidagi zamonaviy texnologik yutuqlar tadqiq qilinadi hamda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarga asoslanib, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan til asistentlari, mobil ilovalar va onlayn interaktiv platformalar kabi raqamli vositalardan foydalanishning afzalliklari, til o'rganishdagi foydalari; shu bilan bir qatorda, ularni o'quv jarayonlariga tatbiq qilishda kelib chiqadigan ba'zi muammolar xususida muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar : xorijiy tillar, innovatsion texnologiyalar, sun'iy intellekt, mobil ilovalar, chet tillarini o'rganishdagi tendensiyalar

Аннотация: В современном мире инновационные образовательные технологии играют важную роль в обучении иностранным языкам, что способствует повышению эффективности учебного процесса. В данной статье исследуются современные технологические достижения в процессе изучения языков, а также на основе проведённых исследований рассматриваются преимущества использования цифровых инструментов, таких как языковые ассистенты на основе искусственного интеллекта, мобильные приложения и онлайн-интерактивные платформы. Кроме того, обсуждаются удобства, которые они предоставляют при изучении языка, а также некоторые проблемы, возникающие при их внедрении в учебный процесс.

Ключевые слова : иностранные языки, инновационные технологии, искусственный интеллект, мобильные приложения, тенденции в изучении иностранных языков.

Annotation: In these days, innovative educational technologies have a crucial role in teaching foreign languages that provide to enhance engagement and effectiveness in this field. This article explores modern technological advancements in learning process. The study shows that digital tools such as artificial intelligence -based language assistants, mobile applications and online interactive platforms. Also, it highlights the benefits of using technologies in teaching which lead to improve learners' language proficiency, meanwhile discussing the challenges educators can face in implementing these technologies into the curriculum. The findings emphasize that making use of digital technologies not only motivates students but also lead to better language acquisition results.

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Keywords: foreign languages, innovative technologies, AI , mobile apps, future trends in learning language.

How language, as well as foreign language, is understood depends on perspective.

Foreign language and teaching has evolved in the digital age as we move from single language to an understanding of learners' language layer levels in a more multilingual society. Foreign language similarly takes on new meaning in the digital age. Foreign language can be perceived as the outside language.

The scope of "foreign" is in comparison to what language counts as native. To understand what counts as foreign language, educators need to consider how contributions from first language (FL), second language (SL), heritage language (HL), as well as dual immersion (DI) and bilingual programs can contribute to a more holistic understanding of language learning. Similarly, in constructing our understanding of language categorizations, researchers should also consider language status, sub ordinance, and dominance in the field and in global societies as well as the consequences of such hierarchies in the digital age. The first language is the inside language or the language of the community in which we live or are born. It is generally understood as the maternal language. However, bilinguals can often speak more than one language that is learned and utilized in a neighborhood - early on. And it is possible that both parents may speak different languages and/or dialects that are learned simultaneously. Having multilingual capability is not uncommon in some countries such as India or Spain. Individuals growing up in the Catalan area of Spain might consider their first language Catalan, and their second language Spanish. Although Catalan is an official language in Spain, the dominant language is Spanish.

In today's modern world the demand for effective foreign language teaching techniques has becoming higher than ever. Traditional teaching methods while still valuable but It often fails to supply various opportunities for learners in an increasingly interconnected world. As a result, innovative educational technologies have appeared as powerful tools to improve language acquirement, making the learning process more efficient, engaging and lively.

The integration of digital sources ,for example, artificial intellegnce (AI) , mobile applications , online interactive platforms has changed language training. these technologies provide intractive learning environments and to allow students to proress at their own pace. Free access to portable, global, cross-cultural,

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individualized and multilingual modes of chat, audio, and visual language interaction exist in most of the world. Broader access to knowledge enables learners to learn independently from formal school education. Despite these advancements, challenges remain in applying them in language education. Factors, for instance, digital literacy, access to resources have to be considered to ensure successful blending into the curriculum. This article explores the latest trends in educational methods, advantages and limitations in detail.

Technological advancements have improved foreign language teaching, making it more engaging and effective. Traditional styles like textbooks and learning by rote are now replaced by digital ones that supporting different learning styles, adaptive learning and giving feedback at once. There are many modern technologies have significantly improved learning foreign languages. As an example of this, AI-based language assistants such as Chat GPT, Google Translate help learners to practice vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation through interactive dialogues. These tools provide instant feedback for learners' progress. Apps like Duo lingo, Quiz-let, Memrise use gamification and interactive exercises to enhance the retention of information and their accessibility allows to practice anywhere conveniently. Websites like Ed X, Coursera, Future Learn, and Khan Academy offer interactive courses with video lessons, quizzes and discussion forums for developing learners' language skills. Students utilize laptop computers for group projects, presentations, and demonstrations in classroom settings as well. With Web 2.0 technology, newly developed software and online chat room make collaboration possible (Richardson, 2007). By using Google Docs, students and teachers can edit the same document online simultaneously or asynchronously, saving time, energy and eliminating the need for physical meetings (Hubbard, 2009).

The Smartboard, an interactive whiteboard motivates students' learning through interaction and promotes willingness to engage in classrooms. Its interactive projection display creates scenarios for language learning (Saine, 2012). Digital markers allow multiple learners to collaborate during storytelling. Notes on the smart board can be saved on computer in digital format (Al-Salem, 2012).

Mobile devices such as the iPad and software apps make language learning portable. Using Pleco apps on a smart phone, Chinese language learners, especially study abroad students, can hand write unfamiliar Chinese characters on a touch screen and look up the meaning in an online digital dictionary. Online dictionaries (e.g., Pleco, Power Word) allow students to hear how a new Chinese character is

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pronounced, see animation of how it is written, read examples of how it is used in sentences, as well as watch videos of how it is used in real life situations.. Game and quiz methods widely used in TV programs in the past are now being utilized to promote learning and assessment in language classrooms. Through smart phone text message polls and mobile voting (e.g., Cahoot), instructors can engage students in sharing their opinions about topics, quickly assess students' learning, and display percentage results on the screen for immediate feedback. With mobile voting, students can find out whether they answered the question correctly and the teacher can also review global classroom student performance results.

Social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), blogs, video-sharing websites (e.g. YouTube) and website builders enable students to absorb vast audio visual information as well as display their creative work. The video chat and text chat function allows foreign language learners to partner with native speakers outside the country and practice speaking online. Wireless internet and smart phone camera also allows learners to stream video images. These types of digital software devices and apps also permit individualized and differentiated language instruction at the student's pace as well as in cooperative and collaborative formats.

Gamification is a strategy that widely used in modern language education. By including game-like elements such as points, leader boards and rewards learning becomes more enjoyable. It can be seen in Duo lingo that keeps users become involved in streaks and encouraging consistent practice by sending messages as a reminder. Gamification promotes the motivation and helps learners to continue on their winning streak. Although these modern technologies have numerous benefits , implementing them into education comes with some certain challenges:

Every teacher must know how to integrate technology effectively into their teaching practices. Most teachers lack digital literacy that result in causing difficult to use advanced tools;

Not all students have equal access to digital devices and the internet due to the personal and situational factors. This situation causes not enabling to stick to their schedule;

Meanwhile, technology gives a great opportunity of increasing our knowledge, deep dependence on it may reduce face to face interaction between people which is important for developing communication skills;

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Many online platforms require the specific personal data to sign up, raising concerns about data protection and privacy. Institutions must be responsible for ensuring ethical use of technology in education.

In conclusion, the integration of innovative educational technologies in foreign language teaching has significantly altered the learning environment making it more highly effective. Digital tools AI, apps, platforms and gamification create new educational opportunities for who all want to learn foreign languages at their own pathways and eager to embrace the latest technology. By utilizing these innovations while maintaining a balance with traditional teaching methods, tutors can create more inclusive language learning environments.

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